

Theory of Consciousness Subject Perspective

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Abstract: The problem of "consciousness" has been explored by philosophers and scientists for thousands of years. Based on the methods of conceptual analysis and principle analysis, this paper puts forward a unique view on the problem of consciousness. First of all, this paper discusses some basic concepts, such as the form of ontology, the character of entity, the Angle of subject, the form of consciousness, and the nature of the objective world. Then, it discusses how all kinds of consciousness emerge from the evolution of basic structure, and analyzes and summarizes the entity structure of each stage. Finally, this paper discusses the principle of consciousness, and analyzes the mechanism and value of consciousness. The systematic discussion and analysis of this paper is of reference value to the understanding of the nature of consciousness.

Keywords: Ontology; Subject perspective; Consciousness; World model

I. The existence of the subject

1.1 Ontology

The definition of ontology: Ontology refers to the eternal, definite, and unique ultimate existence that encompasses all things existing in the spatial and temporal dimensions.

The Infinity of Ontology: Ontology has infinity, encompassing all possible existences and variations.

Evolutionary nature of ontology: The internal elements of ontology can form different forms, and its internal structure can undergo complex changes in the time dimension.

1.2 Entity theory

Definition of entity: An entity is a structure of continuous differences in different dimensions of a large spatiotemporal ontology.

The existence of entities: The essence of the existence of entities lies in their differences. Differentiation is a manifestation of the concept of existence, without differences there is no existence.

Interactivity of entities: The relationship between entities and systems is continuous, and the form of entities and the form of the relationship between systems have a mutual influence, which is called basic interaction.

Subjectivity of Entity: The existence of an entity is equivalent to the existence of its subject. The essence of subject existence lies in its interactivity, and the form of

subject existence is the content of its subject perspective, that is, its subjective content.

1.3 Subjectivity theory

The definition of subject perspective: In an infinite dimensional ontology system, each entity has a specific subject perspective, and the content changes of this perspective correspond to the changes in the entity structure.

The authenticity of the subject perspective: The change in the subject perspective is the only true perception of the entity's interaction with the outside world. The content of the subjective perspective is different from the objective perspective of the third party, which is an abstract simulation of the entity, while the former is the only real existence that the entity can sense.

1.4 Objectivity theory

Consciousness of the objective world: Consciousness is the manifestation of changes in the content of the subject perspective, especially manifested as manifest consciousness in animals. The change of consciousness corresponds to the structure of neural networks, which can simulate the changes of external things, form abstract world models, and adapt to external changes.

Epistemology of the objective world: The objective world in cognition is actually a model constructed based on subjective experiences from the perspective of the subject. It abstracts concepts of things through fixed characteristics of sensory changes, forming a framework, namely the world model, and thus forming the objective world in our understanding.

The consistency of the objective world: Complex entities, through interactions such as visual and tactile senses, map their own sensory states to external object images, forming the so-called objective world. The spatiality of this objective world comes from the abstraction of the consistency between visual and tactile changes.

The simulation of the objective world: The so-called world models are all based on the simulation of infinite dimensional entities from the perspective of the subject, and the content obtained is not realistic. The subjective perspective can only correspond to its own changes, and the external world in cognition is a world model established for changes.

II. Evolution of entities

The evolutionary environment of entities: An infinite ontology serves as an environmental system, where its internal entities can form diverse forms and its

internal structure can vary in complexity over time. The evolution process of entities is a continuous development process, starting from basic interactions, and each stage is a natural extension of the previous stage. The characteristics and driving mechanisms of each stage determine the possibility and direction of its evolution towards higher stages.

The formation of consciousness through entity evolution: Under natural competition, highly adaptive negative feedback structures continue to evolve and develop, with the direction of simulating the complexity of natural changes and preparing as early as possible to cope with them. The form of a unified consciousness intelligent agent helps to improve the degree of adaptability.

Stage 1: self-organizing Entity structure evolution process: natural basic interactions evolve to form adaptive structures

Entity structure: Basic material structure

Entity phenomena: forming complex vibration systems from micro to macro scales.

Driving mechanism: spatiotemporal field characteristics.

Phenomenon principle: The fundamental interactions of nature drive the combination of entities through the characteristics of spatiotemporal fields, forming more complex systems.

Entity structure: Self expanding particle structure

Entity phenomenon: spontaneous and continuous expansion of its own structure, especially the self replication mode.

Driving mechanism: spontaneous attraction and repulsion.

Phenomenon principle: Self expanding Entity structures achieve self replication and structural expansion through spontaneous attraction and repulsion.

Entity structure: Single cell self-organizing structure

Physical phenomenon: adaptive, relying on multi steady state structure and negative feedback regulation.

Driving mechanism: The composite physical effect of the profit seeking and harm avoiding characteristics of composite structures.

Phenomenon principle: Single cell self-organizing structures achieve self adaptation and self maintenance through a complex physical effect of seeking benefits and avoiding harm.

Stage 2: Natural Training Collaborative Structure Evolution Process: Adaptive Structure Collaborative Feedback Experience Evolution to Form Intelligent System

Entity structure: Multi cell collaborative aggregation intelligent agent

Physical phenomenon: Cell aggregation, collaborative feedback of individual cell aggregation, forming a unified overall feedback intelligent system.

Driving mechanism: Experience in naturally training multi cell combination structures.

Phenomenon principle: Multi cell synergistic aggregates form a unified collaborative feedback mechanism through natural training.

Stage 3: Consciousness Unified Subjective Evolution Process: Cell Network Evolution Forming Consciousness Attention Unified Subjective Content Pattern

Entity structure: cellular network subject perspective, unified consciousness, intelligent agent

Physical phenomenon: Consciousness feedback system, where the cellular network forms a unified consciousness feedback system through the mechanism of conscious attention.

Driving mechanism: External changes form the maximum emotional drive for overall response through the attention mechanism and form a memory cycle iteration.

Phenomenon principle: The attention mechanism in the consciousness neural network is associated with the induction of emotions, memory experiences, and forms a holistic response pattern.

III. The principle of consciousness

The definition of consciousness: Consciousness is the change in content that occurs from the perspective of the subject. Consciousness generally refers to the conscious state of animals that can be directly perceived. In animals with explicit consciousness, the neural network entities on which explicit consciousness relies, and the content changes from the subject perspective, are the explicit consciousness itself. This neural network can not only recognize the characteristics of external changes, but also simulate the things that affect it from the perspective of the subject.

The world model in consciousness: There is a close relationship between the world model in consciousness and the changes in the subjective perspective content of neural networks, and it corresponds one-to-one with the changes in the subjective structure, that is, with the changes in the neural network structure. This type of neural

network not only includes networks that process visual and tactile information, but also partially maps the characteristics of external things and simulates their changes, thus constructing an abstract world model. This model is crucial to the formation of the concept of space, which enables organisms to more effectively simulate external changes and adjust their own state to adapt to the external environment.

The process of consciousness generation: In the sensory network of the subject perspective, some sensory structures remain relatively stable and continuously activated in the overall structural changes, similar to the foreground in the background, activating the feature recognition network. The feature recognition network further associates and activates the emotion network, which mutually promote each other in a positive manner, forming a composite sensory network structure with instantaneous maximum activation. The maximum activation structure activates the concept synthesis network, and the continuous activation of the concept synthesis network over time activates the experience network in chronological order. The experience network is constantly changing, and every moment is associated with the activation of the largest composite sensory network structure. Therefore, every moment of the experience network is the maximum activation structure of the neural network. The continuous changes in the experience network are manifested in the clearest content changes from the perspective of the subject, which is precisely the conscious content.

IV. The mechanism of consciousness

The operation process of consciousness: The consciousness neural network unifies various reflex arc neural networks to form a unified maximum reflex direction response to external changes. The attention model in the consciousness neural network selects the most activated sensory network, the experiential memory model predicts changes experienced based on emotional mapping memory, the conceptual understanding model actively predicts unknown changes, the regularity model has the best judgment of comparative experience, the principle system model has systematic causal logic, and the panoramic reflection framework has self referential and consistent completeness.

Consciousness Attention Model: The consciousness attention model is a filtering mechanism that selects the strongest sensation from numerous sensations as consciousness content, ensuring that consciousness content is unique and unified.

Experiential Memory Model: The experiential memory model is based on emotional mapping memory and predicts changes that individuals have experienced. This model allows individuals to predict possible future reactions based on past emotional experiences and memories, thereby making decisions with the highest probability of being correct and achieving the goal of seeking benefits and avoiding harm.

Concept understanding model of things: The concept understanding model of things actively predicts unknown changes. It analyzes the changes that have not been experienced as a whole, uses empirical memory to judge the importance, and predicts the correct response with the highest probability to achieve maximum benefit avoidance.

Rule model: The rule model has the best judgment of comparative experience. It forms the best judgment of rules by comparing individual experiences to guide individual behavior and decision-making.

Principle system model: The principle system model has systematic causal logic, which helps individuals understand and predict changes in complex systems by constructing a causal relationship network.

The panoramic reflection framework: The panoramic reflection framework has self referential and consistent completeness, allowing individuals to reflect on their own experiences and behaviors from a broader perspective, ensuring that their cognition and behavior are self consistent.

V. Motivation of consciousness

The evolutionary characteristics of entities: As a product of natural evolution, entity forms inevitably tend to maintain their own better survival. The objects of this maintenance can be individuals, collectives, and interactive patterns. As long as these different levels of formal characteristics are diverse, they can be selectively evolved by nature.

The formation of conscious motivation: As a specific entity form, the self is determined by natural evolution to have a specific mechanism that tends to maintain its own better survival. After the formation of neural networks in organisms, the effect of neural networks on other physiological systems is a driving force. After the evolution of neural networks into a consciousness unified content synthesis network, the driving

force of this neural network is understood as motivation from its subjective perspective.

The characteristics of conscious motivation: The formal feature of conscious motivation is to seek benefits and avoid harm, the value of conscious motivation to oneself is to promote longer-term survival, and the subjective perspective of conscious motivation is to pursue a longer-term state of happiness.

The implementation method of conscious motivation: The key to pursuing a longer lasting state of happiness lies in how to be happy and how to maintain this state for a longer period of time. The happiness state mainly comes from knowledge of nature, emotions towards life, and desires for feelings. The method of maintaining a longer lasting state of happiness requires continuous selection of behaviors that are most conducive to survival and can obtain happiness based on the real situation.

VI. The Value of Consciousness

The individual value of consciousness: Consciousness is not just a passive response to current stimuli, but an active and predictive system that can use past experiences to predict and adapt to future changes. This integrated consciousness model helps individuals make more effective decisions and behavioral responses in complex and changing environments.

Consciousness attention forms unified feedback: The attention mechanism selects the strongest signal from numerous sensory inputs as the content of consciousness, ensuring the consistency and uniqueness of the content, that is, at any given moment, there is only one dominant feeling or thought in consciousness. The unity of this overall feeling helps to coordinate individual responses to stimuli, making the overall response more unified and effective.

Maximum overall emotional evaluation: The process of emotional evaluation forms an individual's motivation and behavior by identifying the strongest emotional reactions. The synthesis of this maximum emotion helps to limit the interference of weaker sensations, avoid conflicts in pheromone secretion, and thus unify to form the strongest emotional drive, guiding the overall behavior of individuals.

The overall feedback experience memory function of consciousness: Changes in consciousness content generate experiences, which further form emotional

experience memory. These memories are crucial for predicting subsequent reactions, as they allow individuals to predict possible future changes based on past experiences and make decisions with the highest probability of being correct, in order to achieve a win-win situation.

The function of the consciousness understanding model: The consciousness understanding model predicts the most probable correct response by analyzing the changes that have not been experienced as a whole. This model actively utilizes empirical memory to determine the importance of new situations and makes maximum probability predictions based on overall sensory analysis, in order to achieve maximum benefit avoidance.

References

No references cited.